

ESCAPE brings together the astronomy, astroparticle and particle physics ESFRI and pan-European communities with aligned challenges of data-driven research and demonstrated capabilities in addressing various stages of data workflow and concerned with fundamental research through complementary approaches.

The ESCAPE Data Science Summer School 2021

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Intro: School Overview

Training of early career scientists is essential for the development of an open science system in the EOSC. The creation and maintenance of high-quality, open software need special consideration. This is tackled within the thematic training event, where young scientists in the field of astronomy, astro-particle and particle physics were taught the necessary ingredients for their software to become a part of open science by experienced code custodians.

Open, free, online and accessible to all

The registrations had no limitations and were completely free. All the lectures content (slides, lectures recordings, code and datasets) were and are still openly accessible online.

Tools (click to access) used for organisation and communication

School target audience & demographics

The ESCAPE School targets any software engineer, data scientist or interested students from ESCAPE communities. The representativity was good with more than 40% of women.

Most of the participants were young scientists and students, that could benefit easily from the online and free access to the lectures.

Participants and teachers came from a large panel of ESCAPE partners.

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[@ESCAPE_EU](https://twitter.com/ESCAPE_EU) [linkedin.com/in/escape-eu](https://www.linkedin.com/in/escape-eu)

School Programme

Success of the School

The school reach and success was large, with more than 1000 registered participants, hundreds of active ones during the school and a very high level of satisfaction.

Future editions

Leveraging the lessons learned from this online school, a hybrid organisation is envisaged for future editions (June 2022, stay tuned)!

GET THE LECTURES

escape2020.github.io/school2021

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Virtual group picture from happy participants.